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**RISK PERCEPTION OF HEALTHCARE WORKERS ON HEPATITIS 'B'
AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE UPTAKE OF ITS VACCINE IN
SELECTED HOSPITALS IN IBADAN, OYO STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The World Health Organization, WHO, estimates that 296 million people were living with chronic hepatitis B infection in 2019, which resulted in 1.5 million new infections each year, and resulted in an estimated 820,000 deaths. Healthcare workers are a high-risk group in terms of exposure to HBV; thus, the observance of the universal safety precautions and vaccination of people at risk is vital. The main objective of this study is to determine the risk perception of healthcare workers on Hepatitis 'B' and their attitudes towards the uptake of its vaccine in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The research design for this study is a descriptive survey, and the study population comprises health workers from Adeoyo Maternity Teaching Hospital, Yemetu, and the University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. A well-structured Likert scale questionnaire was used for the study, and 240 health workers, which include doctors, nurses, medical laboratory personnel, and community health extension workers, were selected for the study using sample random sampling and proportionate sampling techniques. The collected data was collated and sorted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. A frequency count and simple percentage were used for the research questions while a Chi-square and ANOVA analysis was carried out on the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings show that Healthcare professionals in both health facilities, UCH, and Adeoyo Maternity Hospital, have heard of or seen colleagues having hepatitis, while doctors and nurses are the two categories of healthcare professionals that are mostly affected by hepatitis 'B' infection. Healthcare professionals show a positive attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccination, approve, and strongly believe that hand washing, wearing of masks, eye protection, use of personal protective equipment, and a safe system for hospital waste management and disposal are helpful practices in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare workers. Other positive attitudes expressed by healthcare professionals include early immunization of healthcare professionals, pre-vaccination serological testing, use of 0, 1, and 6-month schedules for vaccination against hepatitis 'B', and post-vaccination testing. Attitude to adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases is positive. Healthcare professionals affirmatively opined that

there should be an adequate supply of PPE and that staff should be involved in selecting personal protective equipment. Adequate dissemination of guidelines on the use of PPE, information, education, and communication on post-exposure management practices, and provision of postexposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures to hepatitis 'B' infection are all essential steps and protective measures to prevent the spread of hepatitis 'B.' here are implications that any health worker with a negative attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine has the likelihood of contracting hepatitis 'B' and any health worker with a negative attitude towards protective measures such as hand washing, PPE will also show no interest in the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine. Despite the positive attitude exhibited by health care professionals, only 16.7% have received all three doses of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' infections.

KEYWORDS: Hepatitis 'B', Healthcare Professionals, Risk perception, knowledge, attitude, and practice.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare workers (HCWs) play an important role in providing prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and care to people in diverse healthcare settings. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), HCWs are all people who are involved in activities that aim at enhancing health, including those who provide health services such as doctors, nurses, laboratory technicians, and pharmacists. Health workers are exposed to several occupational hazards in healthcare settings, including biological, chemical, ergonomic, physical, and stress/violence (WHO, 2020). Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), also known as nosocomial infections, have been reported to be a serious problem in healthcare services as they are common causes of illness and mortality among hospitalized patients including healthcare workers (HCWs) (Department of Health, State Government of Victoria, Better Health Channel, 2019).

Healthcare workers face the occupational risk of exposure to infection with blood-borne pathogens during their routine work in the wards, intensive care units, emergency/trauma triage, and so forth. Worldwide, almost three million HCWs experience exposure to blood-borne pathogens each year (World Health Report, 2012). Despite infection control precautions, healthcare providers remain at risk of acquiring blood-borne infections (Rice, Tomkins and Ncube, 2015)

Globally, there are 136 million workers in the health and social work sector, approximately 70% of whom are women. All these workers have the right to decent work, including protection of health and safety risk at work. Health workers face a range of occupational risks associated with biological, chemical, physical, ergonomic, and psychosocial hazards affecting the safety of both health workers and patients (WHO, 2023).

Hospital-acquired infections worldwide are a major public health problem, leading to increased morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs. Hospitals are a major source of infection risk when providing healthcare services (Alshagrawi and Alhodaithy, 2024). WHO (2022) acknowledged that healthcare settings can contribute to the spread of infections, harming patients, health workers and visitors, if insufficient attention is paid to infection prevention and control (IPC). If good hand hygiene and other cost-effective practices are followed, 70% of those infections can be prevented (WHO, 2022).

Health Care Workers (HCWs) are prone to infection of blood-borne pathogens whenever they come in contact with infected body parts, blood, and body fluids in the course of carrying out their duty (Lee et al, 2017). Most occupational exposure to blood pathogens usually occur percutaneously, mucocutaneous, or through blood contact with non-intact skin (Joseph et al., 2020). Similarly, it has been estimated that about 2.5% of HIV cases and 40% of HBV and HCV cases among HCWs worldwide are the result of these exposures (Agofure and Adidatimi, 2017).

Hepatitis is an inflammation of the liver mainly caused by the Hepatitis B Virus (HBV). The Hepatitis B virus is a global problem, with 66% of the world's population living in areas where there are high levels of infection. The Hepatitis B virus is a very important public health problem, the viral hepatitis pandemic takes a heavy charge on lives, communities, and health systems. Thus, Hepatitis B infection is one of the major public health concerns, which causes serious health problems globally (Garzillo *et al.*, 2020).

Schweitzer *et al.*, (2015) reported that more than 2 billion people have been infected with HBV worldwide, and that 248 million of these people are chronically infected. As reported by WHO (2014), data across 187 countries showed that the estimated number of deaths from viral hepatitis increased from 1.1 million in 2019 to 1.3 million in 2022. Out of these values, 83% were caused by hepatitis B. Every day, there are 3500 people dying globally due to hepatitis B infections.

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is an enveloped virus of the Hepadnavirus family that infects the liver, causing hepatocellular necrosis and inflammation. HBV, spread by percutaneous or mucosal exposure to infected blood and various body fluids, can cause either an acute or chronic disease (Kathleen and Kathleen, 2018). An estimated 257 million people are living with HBV (WHO, 2018), and about 20%–30% of those who become chronically infected will develop complications. Currently, available treatments fail to eradicate the virus in most of those treated, necessitating potentially lifelong treatment, and approximately 650,000 people die annually due to chronic hepatitis B (WHO, 2015). By 2019, WHO estimated that 296 million people were living with chronic hepatitis B infection, which resulted in 1.5 million new infections each year, and resulted in an estimated 820,000 deaths.

HBV is contagious and easy to transmit from one infected individual to another by blood contact, mother to child, unprotected sexual intercourse, sharing of eating utensils, and even barbershops and beauty salon equipment (Mesfin, Kibret and Schildgen, 2014). Hepatitis B is mainly transmitted through prenatal infection, skin, and mucous membrane infections caused by contaminated blood or body, sexual contacts, and injectable drug abusers. Also, tattooing, ear piercing, acupuncture, and dialysis are procedures that increase the risk of infection. HBV is the leading risk factor for HCC globally and accounts for at least 50% of cases of HCC (Katamba and Onaluwa, 2022)

Chronic liver disease due to hepatitis B virus (HBV) accounts for the majority of HCC cases and is thus highly amenable to preventive measures. Hepatitis B infection mainly affects the liver. interrupts the liver's ability to perform vital functions and causes both acute and chronic diseases (Lu, Seto, Zhu, Lai and Yuen, 2013). The burden of hepatitis B infection is highest in the WHO Western Pacific Region and the WHO African Region, where 116 million and 81 million people, respectively, are chronically infected. Sixty million people are infected in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean Region, 18 million in the WHO South-East Asia Region, 14 million in the WHO European Region, and 5 million in the WHO Region of the Americas (WHO, 2022).

Hepatitis B is an important occupational hazard for healthcare workers (HCW). In some studies, HCWs have been shown to have an up to four-fold increased risk of acquiring HBV infection (Jha, Chadha, Bhalla, and Saini, 2012). The main risk factor for contracting HBV infection for HCWs is direct contact with infectious material, especially HBV-infected blood, or via a needle stick injury with HBV-contaminated body fluids (Pellissier, *et al.*, 2012). In particular, recapping hollow-bore needles appears to increase the risk of needle stick injuries. Other studies have reported a lack of awareness of HBV among HCWs; consequently, proper precautions (e.g., use of disposable gloves) against blood-borne infections are lacking in these workers. This observation is consistent with other studies demonstrating that untrained individuals are more likely to be exposed to HBV infection (Ziraba, *et al.*, 2013).

Healthcare workers (HCWs) are at high risk of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) transmission. Hepatitis B vaccination is effective in protecting against HBV infection. Different factors influence HCW vaccination status such as lack of knowledge and awareness, cost, availability, accessibility, and hesitancy. Healthcare workers (HCWs), who are frequently in contact with blood and other body fluids in the course of their work, are at a higher risk of exposure to blood-borne viral diseases such as HBV, hepatitis C virus, and HIV (WHO, 2013). Among the HCWs worldwide, about two million are exposed and about 70 000 are infected with HBV annually. The WHO global burden of the disease showed that 37% of HBV among HCWs was due to occupational exposure resulting from sharp injuries. More than 90% of these infections occur in developing countries such as Nigeria.

The risk of occupational infections in Nigeria is intensified by a variety of factors, comprising but not restricted to overcrowding in hospitals, lower HCW to patient ratio, insufficient or absence of basic safety and protection equipment, re-utilising /re-processing contaminated needles and sharp instruments, and partial awareness of the risk of exposure to blood and body fluid. Prevention remains a recommended safeguard against an epidemic of viral hepatitis. The knowledge and attitudes of the clinician play a key role in the prevention and spread of infection. By knowing the facts and having proper awareness and attitudes, the menace of this disease can be prevented to a great extent. Therefore, this study seeks to determine the risk perception of hepatitis 'B' and the attitude of health workers toward the uptake of its vaccine

METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study was a descriptive survey. A descriptive design was adopted for this study as the method helps to obtain firsthand information regarding the risk perception, prevalence, distribution, determinants, and interrelationship of variables within the population. Therefore, a descriptive survey was used to determine the relationship between the variables of interest (attitude of health workers toward the uptake of the hepatitis vaccine and the uptake of the hepatitis vaccine). The study population comprised of health workers from the selected secondary and tertiary healthcare institutions in Ibadan. The study used a self-structured questionnaire to gather data from participants which were selected from two hospitals in Ibadan.

The University College Hospital (UCH) and Adeoyo Maternity Teaching Hospital were sample population of the study. UCH was formally commissioned after completion on 20 November 1957. The University College Hospital, Ibadan was initially commissioned with 500-bed spaces. Currently, the hospital has 850 bed spaces and 163 examination couches with occupancy rates ranging from 55-60%. Since its inception, the hospital has trained over 6,000 Doctors, 501 Dentists, 4,513 Nurses, 2,307 Midwives, 471 Peri-Operative nurses, 1,062 Laboratory Scientist, 576 Environmental Health officers Tutors, 451 nurse/midwives/Public health educators, 326 Primary Health Care Tutors, 590 Community Health Officers, 640 Physiotherapists, 551 Health Information Management Personnel. The hospital has about 65 service and clinical departments and runs 96 consultative outpatient clinics a week in 50 specialty and sub-specialty disciplines. In addition to the College of Medicine, the Hospital "houses" a Virology Research laboratory, a WHO Collaborating Centre in Immunology, and an Institute of Advanced Medical Research and Training (IAMRAT). The hospital also houses the Special Treatment Clinic (STC), a state-of-the-art clinic for research, training, and treatment of Sexually Transmitted Diseases, and runs clinics for people living with HIV/AIDS.

Adeoyo Maternity Teaching Hospital was established in 1928, It was formerly used as a college hospital by the then University of Ibadan between 1948 and 1954 when it was upgraded with an additional fifty beds, X-Ray annex, laboratory, mortuary and medical lecture rooms. The hospital provides maternal and child

healthcare services to people in Ibadan and its environs. It is made up of antenatal clinic, antenatal ward, labor ward, lying in ward, gynecological ward, post-caesarian section ward, children's ward, immunization clinic, gynecological clinic, and family planning clinic.

- **Sample Size Determination and Sampling Technique**

The sample size was determined using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \frac{pq}{d^2}}{d^2}$$

Where,

n = minimum sample size

Z = Z score corresponding to 95% level of significance i.e., 1.96

P = 0.02

q = complementary probability of $P = 1 - p$

d = degree of precision required = 5%

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.2 \times 0.8}{(0.05)^2}$$

$n = 218$

Adding non-response rate of 10% = $218 + 22 = 240$

The sampling technique was divided into two stages:

Stage I – Sample random sampling was used to select one secondary health institution and one tertiary health institution.

Stage II –proportionate sampling technique was used to select respondents based on available numbers in each health institution.

- **Inclusion Criteria** –Nurses, Doctors, Community health Officers, and Medical Laboratory personnel.
- **Exclusion Criteria** – Other care workers that are not involved in the direct treatment of patients such as administrative staff, health assistants, record officers, etc.

- **Procedure for Data Collection and Data Analysis**

The data collection was done by the researcher and two other trained research assistants. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents and on-the-spot collection was done. The data-gathering process lasted for two months. After data collection, collation, and sorting, data was inputted into a computer software package called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). A frequency count and simple percentage were used for the research questions while a Chi-square and ANOVA analysis was carried out on the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

This session presents the descriptive analyses of data. The simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used for the descriptive analyses of both demography data and research questions. 251 questionnaires were distributed and collected back for analyses but eleven (11) were incomplete and were removed from the data analyses. However, only 240 questionnaires were used for the data analyses.

- **Demographic Data**

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Socio-Demographic Characteristics	Categories	Frequencies (n=240)	Percentage (%)
Age Range	20 – 29 years	91	37.9
	30 – 39 years	81	33.8
	40 – 49 years	22	9.2
	50 years and above	46	19.2
Religion	Christianity	116	48.3
	Islam	124	51.7
	African Traditional Religion	0	0.0
Marital Status	Single	118	49.2
	Married	122	50.8
	Divorced	0	0.0
	Separated	0	0.0
Number of children	None	122	50.8
	1-2Children	27	11.3
	3 children and above	91	37.9
Designation	Nurses	65	27.1
	Doctors	54	22.5
	Community Health Officers	93	38.8
	Medical Laboratory Personnel	28	11.7
Years of professional service	1-5 years	169	70.4
	6 -10 years	55	22.9
	11-15 years	12	5.0
	16 years and above	4	1.7

The information contained in Table 1 showed that healthcare workers aged 20 – 29 years had the highest 91(37.9%) age range who participated in this study. This was followed by those between the ages of 30–39 years, 81 (33.8%) while those that were above 50 years, 46 (19.2%) were next in rank in terms of participation in the study and those within the age 40 – 49 years, 22(9.2%) had the lowest number of participants in this study. From the religious perspective, 116(48.3%) are Christians while 124 (51.7%) are Islam by inclination; none of the respondents are into any form of traditional practices. The marital status of respondents indicates that 122 (50.8%) are married and 118 (49.2%) are single, no respondents indicate either divorced or separated.

The number of children had by respondents shows that the majority 122(50.8%) are yet to have any child, 27(11.3) have 1-2 children, and 91(37.9%) have three children and above. The distribution of health workers that took part in this study shows that 65 (27.1%) are Nurses, 54(22.5%) are Doctors, 93 (38.8%) are Community Health Officers, and Medical Laboratory Personnel are 28(11.7%). The years of professional service of respondents shows that 169(70.4%) have 1-5 years of working experience, 55

(22.9%) have been working within 6 -10 years, and 12 (5.0%) have 11-15 years, while 4 (1.7%) have more than 16 years working experience

Table 2: Incidence of Hepatitis 'B' and Testing among Healthcare Workers

Questions	Categories	Frequencies (n=240)	Percentage (%)
Is there any member of your family with a history and diagnosis of Hepatitis	Yes	6	2.5
	No	234	97.5
	Total	240	100.0
Relative having Hepatitis 'B'	Not Applicable	234	97.5
	Mother	5	2.1
	Father	1	0.4
	Spouse	0	0.0
	Other	0	0.0
	Total	240	100.0
Have you received a diagnostic test for Hepatitis B	Yes	84	35.0
	No	156	65.0
	Total	240	100.0
Year of Diagnostic Test for Hepatitis	Not Applicable	156	65.0
	Within 1 -3 Years Ago	65	27.1
	Within 4 - 6 Years Ago	10	4.2
	Within 7 - 9 Years Ago	9	3.7
	10 years and above	0	0.0
		240	100.0
Have you ever tested positive for Hepatitis B	Yes	0	0.0
	No	240	100.0
		240	100.0

According to Table2 above, 234 (97.5%) indicated that there was no member of their family with a history and diagnosis of hepatitis. Furthermore, 234 (97.5%) reported that there was no member of their relations having hepatitis ‘B’, 5(2.1%) reported that their mother had a history and diagnosis of hepatitis, while 1(0.4%) opined that the father had a history and diagnosis of hepatitis. Eighty-four 84 (35.0%) respondents had received a diagnostic test for hepatitis B. The year of receiving hepatitis diagnosis showed that 65 (27.1%) received a hepatitis diagnosis within 1 - 3 years ago, while 10(4.2%) received a hepatitis diagnosis within 4 - 6 years ago and 9(3.7%) have received hepatitis diagnosis within 7 - 9 years ago. Also, none of the sampled healthcare professionals had ever tested positive for hepatitis B.

• **Answers to the Research Questions**

Three research questions raised in the study were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, mean, and standard deviation scores. This section, therefore, discusses the answers to the research questions as follows:

➤ **Research Question One: What is the level of risk perception of hepatitis ‘B’ among healthcare workers in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State?**

The first research question sought to identify the level of risk perception of hepatitis ‘B’ among healthcare workers in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State. To achieve this, five risk perception questions were analyzed using the standard deviation. Thus, respondents were asked to indicate their risk perception of hepatitis ‘B’. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Risk Perception on Hepatitis B

		YES		NO		Don’t know		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation
		N	%	N	%	N	%		
1	Do you think Hepatitis ‘B’ do occur among healthcare workers	224	93.3	12	5.0	4	1.7	1.083	0.447
2	Have you heard or seen a colleague having hepatitis ‘B’	117	48.8	122	50.8	1	0.4	1.517	1.021
3	Do you think nurses and doctors are more at risk of contracting hepatitis ‘B’ than other healthcare workers	213	88.8	21	8.8	6	2.5	1.138	0.57
4	Do you think the occurrence of hepatitis ‘B’ is high among health workers	72	30.0	155	64.6	13	5.4	1.754	1.271
5	Is the incidence of hepatitis ‘B’ increasing among health workers	57	23.8	160	66.7	23	9.6	1.858	1.381

Table 3 above shows the measurement of standard variation. A standard deviation is a measure of how dispersed the data is about the mean. A standard deviation close to zero indicates that data points are very close to the mean, whereas a larger standard deviation indicates data points are spread further away from the mean. Low or small, standard deviation indicates that data are clustered tightly around the mean.

The risk perception of hepatitis ‘B’ among the 240 health workers, those who think Hepatitis ‘B’ does occur among healthcare workers (\bar{x} = 1.083), were in the majority (93%) while those who have heard of or

seen a colleague having hepatitis ‘B’ (\bar{x} = 1.517) represented only 48.8% of the respondents. About half

(50.8%) of the respondents had not seen any health worker diagnosed with hepatitis ‘B’. Those who

believed that nurses and doctors are more at risk of contracting hepatitis ‘B’ than other health care workers (\bar{x} = 1.138), were in the majority (88.8%).

On the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis ‘B’ among health workers, responses showed that most (64.6%) of the health workers do not think the occurrence of hepatitis ‘B’ is high among health workers (\bar{x} = 1.271), and 66.7% of them do not think that the incidence of hepatitis ‘B’ is increasing among health workers (\bar{x} = 1.381).

Observing the standard variation on items in Table3, there is an indication that there is less variability in the data set on the risk perception of hepatitis ‘B’, as most of the standard variation values are close to zero, demonstrating that the values are relatively consistent for most of the item. However, most health workers do not think the occurrence of hepatitis ‘B’ is high among health workers, and the incidence of hepatitis ‘B’ is not increasing among health workers, but nurses and doctors are more at risk than other health professionals.

Research Question Two: What kind of attitude do health workers show towards the uptake of the hepatitis ‘B’ vaccine in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State?

Research question two sought to determine the attitude health workers showed towards the uptake of the hepatitis ‘B’ vaccine in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State. The result is presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4: Attitude of health workers towards Hepatitis ‘B’ Prevention

		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean (\bar{x})	SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
1	Hepatitis ‘B’ cannot be prevented among healthcare workers	23	9.6	9	3.8	0	0	50	20.8	158	65.8	4.30	3.97
2	It is a waste of time trying to prevent hepatitis ‘B’ among health workers because no matter what it will still happen	1	0.4	10	4.2	0	0	37	15.4	192	80	4.70	4.23
3	Most healthcare workers do not practice safe hygiene adequately	25	10.4	40	16.7	8	3.3	22	9.17	145	60.4	3.93	3.70
4	Wearing of gloves is not a regular practice among health care workers	27	11.3	45	18.8	92	38.3	41	17.1	35	14.5	3.05	2.76

5	Healthcare workers frequently get injured with needle stick and they do not really care about the effect it will have to them	30	12.5	32	13.3	86	35.8	50	20.8	42	17.5	3.18	2.90
6	Hepatitis 'B' infection should not be taken seriously	13	5.4	17	7.1	93	38.7	37	15.4	80	33.3	3.64	3.31
7	Hepatitis 'B' infection will ever be part of health worker life	18	7.5	21	8.8	96	40.0	72	30	33	13.7	3.34	2.99
8	Hand washing after any direct contact with patients is essential to preventing hepatitis 'B'	109	45.4	21	8.8	0	0	11	4.58	99	41.2	2.88	3.00
9	Safe collection and disposal of sharps reduces the spread of hepatitis 'B'	93	38.8	146	60.8	1	0.417	0	0	0	0	1.62	1.11
10	Wearing a mask, eye protection and a gown if blood or other body fluids might splash is helpful in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B'	126	52.5	113	47.1	1	0.417	0	0	0	0	1.48	0.98
11	Personal protective equipment should be disposed of safely	116	48.3	123	51.3	1	0.417	0	0	0	0	1.52	1.02
12	Involvement of staff in the selection of personal protective equipment helps in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B'	112	46.7	119	49.6	1	0.417	8	3.33	0	0	1.60	1.19
13	A safe system for hospital waste management and disposal contributes in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B'	108	45.0	131	54.6	1	0.417	0	0	0	0	1.55	1.06

As shown in Table4, the attitude of health workers towards the uptake of hepatitis ‘B’ vaccination among the 240 respondents showed that a majority (86.6%) disagreed that hepatitis ‘B’ cannot be prevented among healthcare workers, while most of them (95.4%) disagreed that it is a waste of time trying to prevent hepatitis ‘B’ among health workers because no matter what you do, infections will still occur. Similarly, a majority (69.6%) disagreed that most healthcare workers do not practice safe hygiene adequately, and only (31.6%) disagreed that wearing gloves is not a regular practice among healthcare workers while a significant proportion (38.3%) of them were undecided on the regularity of gloves wearing among health workers. Data further showed that most (38.3%) of the respondents disagreed that healthcare workers frequently get injured with needle sticks and they did not care about the effect it will have on them. A significant proportion of respondents (48.7%) also disagreed that hepatitis ‘B’ infection should not be taken seriously, while a (43.7%) of them disagreed that hepatitis ‘B’ infection will ever be part of health worker life.

Furthermore, healthcare professionals showed a positive attitude towards basic activities such as hand washing as a majority (54.2%) agreed that hand washing after any direct contact with patients is essential to preventing hepatitis ‘B’, most (90.8%) of them agreed that safe collection and disposal of sharps reduces the spread of hepatitis ‘B’, majority (99.5%) opined that wearing a mask, eye protection and a gown, if blood or other body fluids might splash, helps reduce the spread of hepatitis ‘B’. Also, virtually all of respondents (99.6%) affirmed that personal protective equipment should be disposed of safely. Almost all (95.7%) of the respondents said the involvement of staff in the selection of personal protective equipment helps in reducing the spread of hepatitis ‘B’. Nearly all respondents (99.6%) agreed that a safe system for hospital waste management and disposal contributes to reducing the spread of hepatitis ‘B’.

Table 5: Attitude toward Hepatitis B Immunization Schedule

		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree			SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	Mean (\bar{x})	
1	Immunize early in the career	218	90.8	22	9.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.09	0.43
2	Pre-vaccination serological testing is unnecessary	22	9.2	39	16.3	5	2.1	49	20.4	125	52.1	3.90	3.65
3	Use 0-, 1-, and 6-months schedule	78	32.5	141	58.8	19	7.9	0	0	2	0.8	1.78	1.35
4	If possible, conduct post-vaccination testing	58	24.2	177	73.8	1	0.4	4	1.67	0	0	1.80	1.30
5	Do not administer boosters routinely	4	1.7	110	45.8	12	5.0	50	20.8	64	26.7	3.25	3.01

Table 5 showed the attitude of healthcare professionals towards the immunization schedule, all (100%) of the respondents agreed that immunization early in the career is good for healthcare professionals (\bar{x} = 0.43).

Majority, 72.5%, affirmed that pre-vaccination serological testing is unnecessary (\bar{x} = 3.65), as almost all (91.3%) of the study participants affirmed that the use of 0, 1, and 6-month schedule for vaccination against hepatitis ‘B’ should be adhered to by the healthcare professionals. Also, a majority, 98%, affirmed that, if possible, post-vaccination testing should be conducted for healthcare professionals.

Research Question Three: What is the level of adherence of health workers to preventive precautions against infectious diseases in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State?

Research question three sought to determine the level of adherence of health workers to preventive precautions against infectious diseases in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State. The result is presented in Tables 6 to 9.

Table 6: Uptake of Hepatitis ‘B’ Vaccination

		YES		NO		Don’t know		Mean (\bar{x})	SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%		
1	I have received one dose of vaccine for hepatitis ‘B’ virus	160	66.3	80	33.8	1	0.4	1.338	0.822
2	I have received more than one dose of vaccine for hepatitis ‘B’ virus	37	15.4	202	84.2	1	0.4	1.85	1.307
3	I have received all three doses of the vaccine for the hepatitis ‘B’ virus	40	16.7	199	82.9	1	0.4	1.838	1.297
4	I have not received any dose of vaccine for hepatitis ‘B’ virus	79	32.5	161	67.5	0	0	1.833	1.291
5	I have not received any vaccine as a health worker	28	11.7	211	87.9	0	0	1.875	1.326

In the rating of responses on the uptake of hepatitis ‘B’ vaccination, 160 (66.3%) have received one dose of vaccine for the hepatitis ‘B’ virus, and only 37 (15.4%) received more than one dose of vaccine for hepatitis ‘B’ virus. Forty, 40 respondents (16.7%) have received all three doses of vaccine for the hepatitis ‘B’ virus, while 79 (32.5%) have not received any dose of vaccine for hepatitis ‘B’ virus and 28 (11.7%) have not received any vaccine as a health worker.

Table 7: Practice of Universal Precautions by Health Workers

		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean (\bar{x})	SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
1	Hand washing after any direct contact with patients is mandatory	223	92.9	10	4.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.01	0.29
2	Safe collection and disposal of sharps is not important	19	7.9	14	5.8	2	0.8	120	50.0	85	35.4	2.73	2.86
3	Gloves for contact with body fluids, non-intact skin and mucous membranes	203	84.6	21	8.8	1	0.417	0	0	15	6.2	1.35	1.20
4	Wearing a mask, eye protection and a gown if blood or other body fluids might splash	151	62.9	16	6.7	0	0	10	4.1	62	25.8	2.22	2.41
5	Gloves for contact with body fluids, non-intact skin and mucous membranes	141	58.8	45	18.8	12	5	16	6.6	26	10.8	1.92	1.91
6	Cleaning up spills of blood and other body fluids is compulsory	221	92.1	19	7.9	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.08	0.40
7	A safe system for hospital waste management and disposal is not so important	117	48.8	10	4.2	0	0	10	4.1	103	42.9	2.88	3.03

Adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases through the practice of universal precautions by healthcare professionals is indicated in Table 7. All respondents (100%) affirmed that hand washing after any direct contact with patients is mandatory, while a majority of them (85.4%) disagreed that safe collection and disposal of sharps is not important. Almost all of the respondents (93.4%) agreed that gloves for contact with body fluids, non-intact skin, and mucous membranes are essential. Furthermore, a higher (69.6%) percentage of respondents opined that wearing a mask, and eye protection is essential in case blood or other body fluids might splash. More than two-thirds of the respondents (77.6%) affirmed that gloves for contact with body fluids, non-intact skin, and mucous membranes are important, and all (100%) of the respondents opined that cleaning up spills of blood and other body fluids is compulsory, and less than half (47.1%) of the respondents said safe system for hospital waste management and disposal is not so important.

Table 8: Availability of Personal Protective Equipment

		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree			SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	Mean (\bar{x})	
1	Ensure adequate supplies	103	42.9	137	57.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.57	1.07
2	Involve staff in the selection of personal protective equipment	98	40.8	142	59.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.59	1.09
3	Train staff in correct use	200	83.3	39	16.3	1	0.4	0	0	0	0	1.17	0.59
4	Use influential senior staff as role models	83	34.6	152	63.3	5	2.1	0	0	0	0	1.68	1.18
5	Monitor compliance and inappropriate use	110	45.8	129	53.8	1	0.4	0	0	0	0	1.55	1.05
6	Dispose safely	118	49.2	121	50.4	1	0.4	0	0	0	0	1.51	1.02

Adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases through the availability of personal protective equipment to healthcare professionals as indicated in Table 8, all (100%) of the respondents affirmed that there should be adequate supplies of PPE and the involvement of staff in the selection of personal protective equipment. Furthermore, almost all (99.6%) agreed that training staff in the correct use of PPE is essential, (97.9%) agreed that using influential senior staff as role models for PPE is good, (99.6%) agreed that monitoring compliance and inappropriate use is important and all (100%) of them agreed that dispose safely of PPE is of utmost priority.

Table 9: Practice of Post-exposure Management Practices in Health Facility

		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree			SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	Mean (\bar{x})	
1	Guidelines that outline all procedures	17	74.9	55	22.9	6	2.5	0	0	0	0	1.28	0.78
2	Dissemination of guidelines	17	72.5	59	24.6	7	2.91	0	0	0	0	1.30	0.82
3	Information, education and communication	18	77.9	53	22.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.22	0.66
4	Support and counseling	19	80.2	48	20.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.20	0.63

5	Where possible, provision of post exposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures	191	79.6	49	20.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.20	0.64
6	Analyze and use surveillance data	198	82.5	33	13.8	0	0	9	3.75	0	0	1.25	0.85

Adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases through the practice of post-exposure management practices in a health facility by healthcare professionals as indicated in Table 9, most (97.5%) of the respondents affirmed that guidelines outline all procedures. Furthermore, almost all (97.1%) agreed that dissemination of guidelines is essential, all (100%) agreed that information, education, and communication on post-exposure management practices is good, all (100%) agreed that support and counseling are important and all (100%) of them agreed that where possible, provision of post exposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures is of almost priority.

- **Test of Hypotheses**

Hypothesis One: There will be no significant relationship between the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B and the attitude of health workers toward the uptake of the hepatitis B vaccine.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics for Hypothesis One

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Perception of the occurrence of Hepatitis B	3.9875	.11133	240
Attitude of Health Workers	37.0833	5.91584	240

Table 11: Corrections Analysis for Hypothesis One

		Correlations	
		Perception of the occurrence of Hepatitis B	Attitude of Health Workers
Perception of the occurrence of Hepatitis B	Pearson Correlation	1	.141*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.029
	N	240	240
Attitude of Health Workers	Pearson Correlation	.141*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.029	
	N	240	240

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 12: Chi-Square test for Hypothesis One

Chi-Square test Tables

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Perception of the occurrence of Hepatitis B	240	3.9875	.11133	3.00	4.00
Attitude of Health Workers	240	37.0833	5.91584	20.00	46.00

Test Statistics

		Perception of the occurrence of Hepatitis B	Attitude of Health Workers
Chi-Square		228.150 ^a	610.325 ^c
Df		1	20
Asymp. Sig.		.000	.000
Monte Carlo Sig.	Sig.	.000 ^b	.000 ^b
	95% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.000
		Upper Bound	.000

The table of correlations above shows that the relationship between the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B virus and the attitude of various health workers was positive. The Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.141 which is significant at 0.05 level of probability. The Chi-square test statistics table also shows the relationship between the occurrence of the hepatitis B virus and the attitude of various health workers towards the uptake of the vaccine. The Chi-square values and the degree of freedom, all indicate the positive relationship between the variables. The p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 the confidence interval value. The results therefore show that there is a significant relationship between the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B virus and the attitude of various health workers towards the uptake of hepatitis B vaccine. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There will be no significant relationship between the attitude of health workers and the uptake of hepatitis ‘B’ vaccine

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics for the Test of Hypothesis Two
Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Attitude of Health Workers	37.0833	5.91584	240
Uptake of Vaccine	8.4125	.86339	240

Table 14: Correlations table for the test of Hypothesis Two

		Attitude of Health Workers	Uptake of Vaccine
Attitude of Health Workers	Pearson Correlation	1	.306**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	240	240
Uptake of Vaccine	Pearson Correlation	.306**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 15: Pearson Correlation table for the test of Hypothesis Two

	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Intervals (2-tailed) ^a	
			Lower	Upper
Attitude of Health Workers – Uptake of Vaccine	.306	.000	.187	.417

a. Estimation is based on Fisher's r-to-z transformation.

**Table 16: Chi-square test of Hypothesis Two
Descriptive Statistics**

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Attitude of Health Workers	240	37.0833	5.91584	20.00	46.00
Uptake of Vaccine	240	8.4125	.86339	6.00	11.00

Test Statistics

	Attitude Of Health Workers	Uptake Of Vaccine
Chi-Square	610.325 ^a	282.350 ^c
Df	20	5
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000
Monte Carlo Sig. Sig.	.000 ^b	.000 ^b
95% Confidence Interval Lower Bound	.000	.000
Upper Bound	.000	.000

The table of correlation between the attitude of health workers and uptake of the Hepatitis B vaccine shows a positive relationship. The Pearson correlation value between the two variables is 0.306. The table of confidence intervals shows a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, this also shows a positive relationship. The chi-square table test statistics also show a significant relationship between the two variables been considered. The p-value in both cases is less than 0.05 which shows a strong relationship. The results therefore show that there is a significant relationship between the attitude of health workers and the uptake of the hepatitis B vaccine. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

• Summary of Findings

Hepatitis ‘B’ infection among health workers remains a big threat to their effectiveness; however, none of the sampled healthcare professionals have ever tested positive for hepatitis ‘B’, and only 2.1% of them reported having a member of their family diagnosed with hepatitis ‘B’, while about half (48.8%) of them have heard or seen a colleague having hepatitis. This makes 64.6% of sampled respondents believe that the occurrence of hepatitis ‘B’ is not high among health workers; however, the majority (88.8%) opined that nurses and doctors are more at risk of contracting hepatitis ‘B’ than other health care workers.

Sampled healthcare professionals showed a positive attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis ‘B’ vaccination as most (86.6%) disagreed that hepatitis ‘B’ cannot be prevented among healthcare workers, 95.4%

disagreed that it is a waste of time trying to prevent hepatitis 'B' among health workers because no matter what it will still happen. Similarly, the majority of healthcare professionals approve and strongly believe that hand washing, wearing of masks, eye protection, use of personal protective equipment, and a safe system for hospital waste management and disposal are helpful practices in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare workers. Other positive attitudes expressed by healthcare professionals include early immunization of healthcare professionals, pre-vaccination serological testing, use of 0, 1, and 6-month schedule for vaccination against hepatitis 'B', and post-vaccination testing.

Furthermore, the attitude to adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases is positive, all (100%) of the respondents affirmed that there should be an adequate supply of PPE and also involve staff in the selection of personal protective equipment. Also, hospital management should use influential senior staff as role models for PPE and monitor compliance and inappropriate use of PPE. In terms of information about PPE, all (100%) of the sampled respondents agreed that there should be adequate dissemination of guidelines on the use of PPE, information, education, and communication on post-exposure management practices, and provision of post exposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures to hepatitis 'B' infection.

Despite, the positive attitude exhibited by the health care professionals only 66.3% of them have received one dose of vaccine for the hepatitis 'B' virus, just 15.4% of them have received more than one dose of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' virus, and 16.7% have received all the three doses of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' virus, while 32.5% of them have not received any dose of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' virus.

Hypothesis analysis further affirmed the descriptive statistics; the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.141 which is significant at a 0.05 level of probability and the p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 the confidence interval value shows that there is a significant relationship between the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B virus and the attitude of various health workers towards the uptake of hepatitis B vaccine. This implies that any health worker with a negative attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine has a likelihood of contracting hepatitis 'B'.

Also, the Pearson correlation between the attitude of health workers and uptake of the Hepatitis B vaccine shows a positive relationship of 0.306; and the p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, also shows a positive relationship. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the attitude of health workers and the uptake of hepatitis B vaccine. This implies that any health worker with a negative attitude towards protective measures such as hand washing, and PPE will also show no interest in the uptake of the hepatitis 'B' vaccine.

Furthermore, the F values =12.273, df = 2, the p-value = 0.000 which is less than 0.05, and the value coefficients of 0.084 for the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B and 0.044 for an attitude of health workers show that there is a significant joint relationship between occurrence and attitude of various health workers towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Contact between healthcare professionals and a patient is inevitable, thus contact-related infections such as hepatitis 'B' might be unavoidable for healthcare professionals. Samuel, Aderibigbe, Salami, and Babatunde (2019) confirmed that Hepatitis B can be acquired as a nosocomial infection from the hospital and Hepatitis B infection is widely transmitted like HIV/AIDS. Thus, this study sought to determine the risk perception of healthcare workers on Hepatitis 'B' and their attitudes towards the uptake of its vaccine in selected secondary and tertiary healthcare institutions in Ibadan. This study like the study of Salman *et al.*, (2021) on hepatitis B vaccination that was carried out in two secondary care hospitals in Pakistan, utilized doctors, nurses, and laboratory workers as respondents. This is an indication that the study of

Hepatitis B as a nosocomial infection from hospitals in developing countries like Nigeria should be the focus of healthcare research. Similarly, Mueller, Stoetter, and Kalluvya (2015) studied the prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among healthcare workers in a tertiary hospital in Tanzania and confirmed that those at risk of contracting HBV via exposure to potentially infectious materials were 79.2 %. This is an indication that safe collection and disposal of sharps reduces the spread and prevalence of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare professionals.

The demographic information of participants showed that the majority (37.9%) of sampled healthcare workers are between 20 – 29 years and are mostly (51.7%) practicing Islamic religion. A larger (50.8%) percentage of them were married with children with Nurses, Doctors, Community Health Officers, and Medical Laboratory Personnel had the sampled healthcare professionals with a majority (70.4%) of them had within 1-5 years of working experience. This is an indication that most participants in this study had prerequisite knowledge and experience as healthcare professionals, an advantage for this study. Samuel, Aderibigbe, Salami, and Babatunde (2019) also substantiate in their study that a majority (75.5%) of respondents were aware of the existence of the Hepatitis B vaccine before the study.

Hepatitis 'B' infection among health workers remains a big threat to their effectiveness; however, none of the sampled healthcare professionals have ever tested positive for hepatitis 'B', and only 2.1% of them reported having had a member of their family diagnosed with hepatitis 'B', while about half (48.8%) of them had heard or seen a colleague of theirs diagnosed with hepatitis. This made 64.6% of the respondents believe that the occurrence of hepatitis 'B' was not high among health workers; however, a majority (88.8%) opined those nurses and doctors were more at risk of contracting hepatitis 'B' than other health care workers. Ogoina *et al.*, (2014) had shown that professional category and previous training in infection control were independently associated with HBV vaccination. Ogoina and colleagues reported that house officers and laboratory scientists were more likely to be unvaccinated than resident doctors, consultant doctors, and nurses. Both doctors and nurses are at higher risk of contracting hepatitis 'B' which could reflect the fact that both doctors and nurses do have more frequent contact with patients than health professionals such as laboratory workers and community health officers.

In this study, the respondents, showed a positive attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccination as most (86.6%) disagreed that hepatitis 'B' cannot be prevented among healthcare workers, 95.4% disagreed that it is a waste of time trying to prevent hepatitis 'B' among health workers because no matter what is done, infection might still occur. Similarly, a majority of healthcare professionals approve and strongly believed that hand washing, wearing of masks, eye protection, use of personal protective equipment, and a safe system for hospital waste management and disposal are helpful practices in reducing the spread of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare workers. These attitudes were similar to those reported by Abdela, *et al.*, (2016), that the uptake of hepatitis B infection prevention activities is a predictor of attitude such as hepatitis B screening, hepatitis B vaccination, post-hepatitis B vaccination antibody testing, changing of gloves per client, non-recapping of needles after use and prevention of blood splashes on the body.

Other positive attitudes expressed by healthcare professionals include early vaccination of healthcare professionals, pre-vaccination serological testing, use of 0, 1, and 6-month schedule for vaccination against hepatitis 'B', and post-vaccination testing. This study corroborates with the findings of Samuel, Aderibigbe, Salami, and Babatunde (2019) revealing that one way of preventing Hepatitis B infection is through preventive measures such as vaccination as was stated by a majority (77.2%) of the respondents. Furthermore, the attitude towards preventive precautions against infectious diseases was positive, all (100%) of the respondents affirmed that there should be adequate supplies of PPE and also involve staff in the selection of personal protective equipment. Also, hospital management should use influential senior

staff as role models for PPE and monitor compliance and inappropriate use of PPE. This finding agreed with Salman *et al.* (2021), that Hepatitis B vaccination should be made a job entry requirement to achieve more complete vaccination numbers.

In terms of information about PPE, all (100%) of the sampled respondents agreed that there should be adequate dissemination of guidelines on the use of PPE, information, education and communication on post-exposure management practices and provision of post exposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures to hepatitis 'B' infection. This finding agrees with Abdela *et al.*, (2016) that indicate knowledge of hepatitis B infection prevention in the context of vaccination and the existence of post-exposure prophylaxis for the management of accidentally exposed persons is essential to the reduction of the spread and prevalence of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare professionals. This study also agrees with the finding of Samuel, Aderibigbe, Salami, and Babatunde (2019) that poor compliance of Health workers to hepatitis B vaccination is an issue that deserves serious attention.

There is a need for health education campaigns for health workers so that they can understand the risks they are exposed to while performing their duties.

Vaccination policies are required to achieve full vaccination for both part-timers and full-timer healthcare workers. About two-thirds, 66.3% of them have received one dose of the vaccine for the hepatitis 'B' virus, a few 15.4% of them have received more than one dose of vaccine for the hepatitis 'B' virus, while 16.7% have received all the three doses of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' virus, while 32.5% of them had not received any dose of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' virus as at the time of completion of this study.

In terms of uptake of the first dose of the Hepatitis B vaccine, the findings of this study agreed with Samuel, Aderibigbe, Salami, and Babatunde (2019), and Salman *et al.*, (2021) with about two-thirds receiving the first dose of the vaccine in secondary care hospitals in Pakistan. The challenge of completing the three-dose schedule remained daunting, especially in developing nations around Africa including this study from Nigeria.

South Sudan, a developing country in Africa reported that the uptake of hepatitis B vaccination was found to be low at 44.20%, only 48.8% had received one dose, 29.1% received two doses, while 22.1% had received all three doses (Alege, Gulom, Ochom and Kaku, 2020). In another study in Kenya, 80% of healthcare workers were vaccinated against HBV, and out of those, only 48% had received all three doses (Kisangau, Awour, and Juma, 2019). This trend suggests that secondary health facilities in developing countries are witnessing a similar pattern of incomplete vaccination among healthcare professionals, and this could be because of improper funding of the health sector.

Moreover, the findings of this study are similar to another study conducted in two teaching hospitals in Jos, North-Central Nigeria, and Yenagoa, South-South Nigeria by Ogoina, *et al.*, (2014) which showed that out of 290 HCWs who participated in the study, 185 (64.5%) had received at least one dose of HBV vaccine; 105 (36.2%) had full coverage of three doses. This showed that lack of completion of hepatitis 'B' vaccination is a general problem in all geographical regions in Nigeria.

This finding agreed with the study conducted by Mueller, Stoetter, and Kalluvya (2015) which concluded that pre-testing might be a useful tool to identify susceptible individuals. It is therefore essential that hospital management should make pre-testing of hepatitis 'B' mandatory because most 156(65.0%) of the sampled healthcare professionals had not received a diagnostic test for Hepatitis 'B', more likely due to lack of enforcement on the part of the management of healthcare institutions.

Hypothesis analysis further affirmed the descriptive statistics; the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.141 which is significant at a 0.05 level of probability and the p-value is 0.000 which was less than 0.05 the confidence interval value showed a significant relationship between the perception of the occurrence of hepatitis B virus and the attitude of various health workers towards the uptake of hepatitis B vaccine. This implied that any health worker with a negative attitude towards the uptake of the hepatitis 'B' vaccine has the likelihood of contracting hepatitis 'B'.

Also, the Pearson correlation between the attitude of health workers and uptake of the Hepatitis B vaccine showed a positive relationship of 0.306; and the p-value of 0.000 which was less than 0.05, also showed a positive relationship. Therefore, there was a significant relationship between the attitude of health workers and the uptake of the hepatitis B vaccine. This implied that any health worker with a negative attitude towards protective measures such as hand washing, and PPE will also show no interest in the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine. This corroborates with Alege, Gulom, Ochom, and Kaku (2020) that reported that the uptake of viral hepatitis B vaccination among healthcare workers shows that knowing that hepatitis B can be prevented by vaccination, availability of vaccines in the health facility, and availability of guidelines followed by all health workers in this facility, were the factors independently associated with the uptake of hepatitis B vaccination. Furthermore, the conclusion from Rav-Marathe, Wan, and Marathe (2016) that effective hepatitis B infection prevention is a product of good attitude and good practice of hepatitis B infection prevention is in agreement with the finding of this study.

CONCLUSION

Healthcare professionals in UCH and Adeoyo Maternity Hospital had heard of or seen colleagues with hepatitis, while doctors and nurses were the two categories of healthcare professionals were most likely to be infected with hepatitis 'B' virus when performing their duties if preventive measures were not taken seriously. Healthcare professionals showed a positive attitude towards the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccination, approved, and strongly believed that hand washing, wearing of masks, eye protection, use of personal protective equipment, and a safe system for hospital waste management and disposal re helpful practices to reduce the spread of hepatitis 'B' among healthcare workers. Other positive attitudes expressed by healthcare professionals include early immunization of healthcare professionals, pre-vaccination serological testing, use of 0, 1, and 6-month schedule for vaccination against hepatitis 'B', and post-vaccination testing. Attitude to adherence to preventive precautions against infectious diseases is positive.

Healthcare professionals affirmatively opined that there should be an adequate supply of PPE and also involve healthcare staff in the selection of personal protective equipment. Adequate dissemination of guidelines on the use of PPE, information, education, and communication on post-exposure management practices, and provision of post exposure prophylactic medication for high-risk exposures to hepatitis 'B' infection were adjudged as essential steps and protective measures to prevent of spread of hepatitis 'B'. There are implications that any health worker with a negative attitude towards the uptake of the hepatitis 'B' vaccine has the likelihood of contracting hepatitis 'B' and any health worker with a negative attitude towards protective measures such as hand washing, and PPE, will also show no interest in the uptake of hepatitis 'B' vaccine. Despite the positive attitude exhibited by the health care professionals, only 16.7% have received all three doses of vaccine for hepatitis 'B' infections.

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